

APPLICATION OF DECLINE CURVE ANALYSIS IN PREDICTING THE LIFE SPAN OF A WELL IN NIGER DELTA RESERVOIR

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ABSTRACT

Decline curve analysis is aimed at predicting well production behaviour at different points in time based on the well past production history. There are three types of decline curve analysis, which are extensively discussed in this paper. This paper focused on determining or extrapolating future production rate of a well using Tega – 3A well as a case study. The well was put on stream in 1970 and produced on J4.0 and J5.0 in 1970. J5.0 was produced to depletion in 1980. It was squeezed off and the well was re-entered in that same year and re-completed on J3.6 and J4.0. The data for this paper were accumulated from J3.6, it had an initial production rate of 1000bbl/day. Its production rate when the data used for this paper was collected was 100bbl/day in the year 2001. J3.6 has since been squeezed off in 2007. This paper will show how decline curve analysis will predict exactly the life span of J3.6, for 27 years that is from 1980 to 2007

KEYWORDS: Well, Life, Span, Analysis, Production

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important tasks of the petroleum engineer is to predict the amounts of oil and gas that will be recovered from a reservoir. There are four basic methods for predicting recoveries future life of a well, with several variations of each. The four methods are volumetric analysis material balance techniques, decline curve analysis and reservoir simulation. These methods differ substantially in complexity, and there are appropriate applications for each of the techniques.

Fetkovich(1980), presented a paper title “Decline curve analysis using type curves”. In his paper, he said the various methods used always have been regarded as strictly empirical and generally not scientific.

The techniques for relating production to time is known as decline curve analysis. There are three types of decline curves, although only two of the three techniques are commonly used. Exponential and hyperbolic production declines occur in many reservoirs(Slider.H.C.,1968). While the third type, harmonic decline, is now believed to be uncommon, the method is still used as a conservative projection technique.

The determination of the most probable future life of a well and the estimate of its future production can sometimes be done by volumetric calculations, but sufficient data are not always available to eliminate all guess work.

In that case, the possibility of extrapolating the trend of some variable characteristics of such a producing well may be considerable help. The simplest and most readily available variable characteristic of a producing well is its production rate, and the logical way to determine the future life of a well by extrapolation is to plot this variable production rate either against time or cumulative production, extending the curves obtained to the economic limit. The point of intersection of the extrapolated curve with the economic limit then indicates the possible future life of the future oil recovery. With the future rate known, it is possible to determine the future total production or reserves of the well. This represents the beginning of the art that is since become more of a science known as decline curve analysis.

The purpose of decline curve analysis is to determine future production and ultimate recovery of wells with some production history (Beal.C.A,1919). Since it depends on a curve-fit of past performance, the accuracy is expected to be greater for a well with several months or years of uninterrupted production history than for a well with only a limited amount of history.

The definition of decline curve can be represented both mathematically and graphically with both, the future life of a well can be determined (PIRSON 1976).

The aims and objectives of this paper are

To show how individual well and field performance trends may be analyzed using decline curve so as to provide information about future production rate; about cumulative rate and most importantly about the remaining oil or gas reserves.

To predict future production rate of well “3A” in Tega field using decline curve analysis.

Arps’ Rate – Time Equation

Nearly all conventional decline curve analysis is based on the empirical rate –time equations given by Arps as:

$$\frac{q(t)}{q_i} = \frac{1}{[1 + bD_i t]^{1/b}} \text{-----1}$$

For b=0, we can obtain the exponential decline equation from equation 1,

$$\frac{q(t)}{q_i} = \frac{1}{e^{D_i t}} \text{-----2}$$

And for b=1, referred to as harmonic decline, we have

$$\frac{q(t)}{q_i} = \frac{1}{[1 + D_i t]} \text{-----3}$$

A unit solution ($D_i = 1$) of Equation 1 was developed for values of b between 0 and 1 in 0.1 increments. The results are plotted as a set of log-log type curves in terms of a decline curve dimensionless rate

$$q_{Dd} = \frac{q(t)}{q_i} \text{-----4}$$

and a decline curve dimensionless time

$$t_{Dd} = D_i t \text{-----5}$$

The nominal decline fraction may readily be converted to other time units with

$$D_1 t_1 = D_2 t_2 \text{-----6}$$

As long as the quantity “Dt” is dimensionless Equation 6 may be solved for the normal decline fraction.

$$D = \frac{[\ln(q_i/q)]}{t} \text{-----7}$$

The cumulative production N_p is the integral from zero to “t” of q dt, it may be calculated using

$$N_p = (q_i - q)/D \text{-----8}$$

Where q_i , q and D all have consist unit. Equation 8 indicates that a Cartesian plot of rate as a function of cumulation production should be linear. This equation may also be employed to determine the nominal decline fraction from the given production data.

$$D = (q_i - q)/N_p \text{-----9}$$

RESERVOIR CHARACTERISTICS AND DECLINE CURVE

In order to analyse what influence certain reservoir characteristics may have on the type of decline curves, it was first assumed that we are dealing with the idealized case of a reservoir, where water drive is absent and where the pressure is proportional to the amount of remaining oil (Kewen,2003). It was further assumed that the productivity index of the wells is constant throughout their life, so that, the production rates are always proportional to the reservoir pressure. In such a hypothetical case, the relationship between cumulative oil produced and pressure would have to be linear and also the relationship between production rate and cumulative production. In most actual reservoirs, however, the above mentioned idealized conditions do not occur. Pressures usually are not proportioned to the remaining oil, but seem to decline at a gradually slower rate as the amount of remaining oil diminishes (Rankin,1943). At the same time the productivity index are generally not constant but show a tendency to decline as the reservoir is being depleted and the gas oil ratios increase. The combined result of these two tendencies is a rate-cumulative relationship, which instead of being a straight line on co-ordinate paper; show up as a gentle curve convex towards the origin.

BRIEF HISTORY OF THE WELL

This well was drilled in June 1970 and was initially completed on J 4.0 and J 5.0 sand in August 1970. The well put on production, until J 5.0 sand was produced to depletion in 1980. The well re-entered in August 1980, J 5.0 sand was squeezed off during well re-entry and the well was re-completed on J 3.6 sand.

The well was later put on stream in November 1980 with an initial production of 1300 barrels of oil per day on J 3.6 sand and 1450 barrels per day on J 4.0 sand. Allowable production at the company discretion was 1000 barrels per day on J 3.6 sand and 1200 barrels per day on J4.0 sand.

WELL COMPLETION METHOD

The well was re-completed as two string dual completions on J 3.6 sand at a depth of 8836ft to 8840ft and J 4.0 sand at the depth of 8890ft to 8896ft. The length of the short string was 8809ft with 278 joints, and the long string was 8886ft with 284 joints.

The reservoir data for well 3A is displayed in Table 1.0.

Table 1.0:Reservoir data for well 3A

Data	Units	J 3.6
Well Status	Status	FTL
Total depth	Ft ah	12805
Maximum Deviation	Deg of ft ah	4.50@5197';
Hole Size	inches	8.5
Sand Exclusion	Type	SCON
Interval	Ft ah	8890
Net oil Sand	Ft	45
Permeability	md	1834
Porosity	%	25
Water Saturation	%	38
Initial Reservoir Pressure	psi	3679
Present Reservoir pressure	Psi	2520
Initial Solution GOR	Scf/bbl	299
Bottom Hole temperature	F	148
Oil Gravity	API	25
Water S.G	60/60	1.02
Perforation density	SPF	4
Perforation diameter	Inches	0.41
Tubing Size weight	In-lbs/ft	23/8-46
Tubing Depth	Ft	8886
Casing Size	In-lbs/ft	7-26
Top packer	Type-ft	A-s-8768

DECLINE ANALYSIS/PRODUCTION RATE OF THE WELL

For the purpose of this study, only the production data of J 3.6 sand is considered. As production continues, the production rate of the J 3.6 sand began to decline as will be seen in the production data in Table 2.0.

For more values consideration, the production rate analysis shall be based or considered at an average of one year interval. As at the first day of production, the well was producing at a rate of 1000bbl/day on the average of the year.

Table 2: Production data

Time (years)	Oil rate BOPD	BEAN 64''	BS&W %	GOR SCF/STB	FTHP PSI	SAND PPTB	CONNE OIL
NOV 80	1000	28	0	299	839	0.0	0.36500
NOV 81	875	28	0	344	607	0.2	0.684375
NOV 82	700	28	12	442	550	0.4	0.939875
NOV 83	750	24	1	449	700	0.4	1.213625
NOV 84	620	28	0	416	400	4.0	1.430925
NOV 85	550	24	1	640	450	0.5	1.640675
NOV 86	550	20	0	451	380	5.7	1.841425
NOV 87	400	20	0	271	500	0.1	1.987425
NOV 88	380	20	1	731	400	0.6	2.126125
NOV 89	343	20	2	391	560	2.3	2.250225
NOV 90	340	24	2	351	420	4.8	2.374325
NOV 91	240	20	2	472	360	1.7	2.461925
NOV 92	240	20	0	595	350	1.0	2.549525
NOV 93	240	20	1	513	360	3.0	2.637125
NOV 94	190	16	0	438	400	2.0	2.706475
NOV 95	200	16	0	432	720	3.0	2.779475
NOV 96	150	20	2	421	500	1.7	2.834225
NOV 97	135	20	2	463	200	1.8	2.8835
NOV 98	120	16	1	361	400	2.6	2.9273
NOV 99	100	16	1	302	500	3.2	2.9638
NOV 2000	95	20	0	345	360	3.1	2.998475
JUN 2001	100	16	2	520	420	2.6	3.034925

ECONOMIC LIMIT OF J 3.6 SAND

Economic limit of a well is an end point. That is a production rate at which a well or field begins to lose money if production continues. This is also called the point of abandonment where it is no longer economical to produce.

The economic limit of the well was put at 40 bbl./day by the company. This means that the well will be abandoned when production rate decline to this level.

PREDICTING THE FUTURE PRODUCTION RATE OF THE WELL

The future production rate of the well (J3.6 sand) can be predicted using decline curve from the available production data a graph of production rate against time is plotted on a semi log graph as shown in fig fig1.0 and extrapolated to give the future production rate as well as the abandonment period of the well.

The use of exponential decline curves analysis fits the production data as the plot of the available production rate data against time gives three possible straight lines A, B and C which can be analysed to choose the best line that will fit the performance of the reservoir.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data displayed in table 2.0 is the production data for J3.6 sand. They are collected based on the average production for each year. The initial production rate of the well (J3.6 sand) was 1000 barrels per day on the average from November 1980 to October 1981. As the year increased, the production rate declined. The

production rate was fairly constant from 1985 to 1986 with an average production of 550 bbl./day for each year. Also, it was constant from 1991 to 1993 with an average production of 240 barrels per day.

These data when plotted on a semi log graph as discussed in chapter 3 gives 3 possible straight lines A, B and C which fits one of the 3 types of decline curve, using constant percentage decline as the graph indicates, a lot of information can be derived from the production data. Analysing the data will also help to determine the mathematical accuracy of the graph as well as the best line that fits the data.

DETERMINATION OF THE ACCURACY OF THE GRAPH

To determine the mathematical accuracy of the graph, and also the best line that fits the data, it is necessary to determine the decline rate of the well from the available production data using mathematical approach and at the same time evaluate decline rate D from the slopes of the graph. Comparison of the values obtained will give the best line that fits the data thereby giving room for meaningful conclusion with the production rate of 550 bbl./day in 1985 and 150 bbl./day in 1996 the decline rate D can be calculated using;

$$q_t = q_i e^{-Dt}$$

Where $t = 1996 - 1985 = 11$ years

$$150 = 550e^{-11D}$$

$$\frac{150}{550} = e^{-11D}$$

$$3.667 = e^{11D}$$

$$11D = \ln 3.667$$

$$D = 0.118/\text{year}$$

Also, with the production rate of 343 bbl./day in 1989 and 190 bbl./day in 1994 decline rate can also be calculated using the same equation;

$$t = 1994 - 1989 = 5 \text{ years}$$

$$190 = 343e^{-5D} \quad \frac{190}{343} = e^{-5D} = e^{5D} = \frac{343}{190}$$

$$1.8053 = e^{5D}$$

$$5D = \ln 1.8053$$

$$5D = 0.5907$$

$$D = 0.118/\text{year}$$

From the graph

$$\text{Slope A} = -\frac{\Delta \ln q}{\Delta t} = -\frac{\ln 340 - \ln 200}{1995 - 1990} = -\frac{5.8289 - 5.2983}{5} = -\frac{0.5306}{5} = -0.106$$

Decline rate (D) = 0.106/year

$$\text{Slope B} = -\frac{\Delta \ln q}{\Delta t} = -\frac{\ln 550 - \ln 150}{1996 - 1985} = -\frac{6.3099 - 5.0106}{11} = -\frac{1.2993}{11} = -0.118$$

Decline rate (D) = 0.0118/year

$$\text{Slope C} = -\frac{\Delta \ln q}{\Delta t} = -\frac{\ln 1000 - \ln 700}{1982 - 1980} = -\frac{6.9078 - 6.5511}{2} = -\frac{0.3567}{2} = -0.178$$

Decline rate (D) = 0.178/year

From the above calculations the straight line B gives the best representation of the well performance data. Line B has the highest number of points and its value of the decline rate is in agreement with what is obtained mathematically from the data.

Therefore, 0.118 is the approximate decline rate of the well J3.6 sand per year.

ABANDONMENT TIME

From the available production data, it shows that the production data is decreasing with time. Presently, the well produces at the rate of 100 barrels per day. This value is recorded as at June 2001, meaning that a time will come when it will not be economically justifiable to produce the well. The production rate at this point is what is described in chapter 3 as the economic limit of the well and is given as 40 bbl./day.

The time taken to reach this limit is the abandonment time and it can be calculated from the available production data, using mathematical approach production rate of abandonment = 40 bbl./day.

Initial production rate = 1000 bbl./day (q_i)

Decline rate = 0.118/year

Using

$$q_t = q_i e^{-Dt} \quad .40 = 1000 e^{-0.118t} \quad \frac{.40}{1000} = e^{-0.118t}$$

$$\frac{1000}{.40} = e^{0.118t} \quad 25 = e^{0.118t}$$

$$0.118t = \ln 25 \quad 0.118t = 3.219$$

$$t = \frac{3.219}{0.118} \quad t = 27 \text{ years}$$

This then implies that the total life span of the well from first year of production to abandonment is 27 years.

Extrapolation the graph could have been useful in giving the approximate time of abandonment if not for the problem of space constraint. Meanwhile, other points could be chosen from the graph for a reasonable conclusion to be drawn from the available data.

As at the time the data used for this work was collected in 2001, the well has been producing for 21 years i.e. 1980 to 2001. Therefore, the life left for this well after 2001 is 27 - 21 = 6 years.

J3.6 has since been squeezed out in 2007.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of decline curve analysis is to determine future production and therefore ultimate recovery of wells with some production history. Since decline curve analysis depends on a curve fit of past performance, the accuracy is expected to be greater for a well with several months or years of uninterrupted production history than a well with only a limited amount of history.

Decline curve is the plot of fraction change in production rate with time. A is a method of prediction future production performance wells, estimation of its cumulative production that depends on one readily available variable. This variable is the production data of the well.

RECOMMENDATION

For the accuracy of prediction the well production behaviour with decline curve analysis, there is need to recommend that:

1. An appreciable period of time should be used to monitor the production rate of the well.
2. Changes in operating practice such as stimulation, secondary recovery, gas lifting, water flooding, and gas injection should be incorporated.
3. The review of the economic limit of the well should be made annually due to changes in product value.

NOMENCLATURE

D = Decline rate
D_i = Initial decline rate
h = Hyperbolic exponent
q = Rate of production
q_t = rate of production at time t
t = Time period between q_i and q_t
Δt = change in time
Δq = change in production rate
DN_p = increment in cumulative production
SCON = sand consolidation
GOR = gas oil ratio
BS&W = basic sediment and water
Psi = pounds per square inch
md = milli Darcy
SCF/BBL = Standard cubic feet per barrel
Lbs. = Pounds
Ft = feet

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Received for Publication: 14/02/2011, Accepted for Publication: 18/03/2011

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